

Revealing the complexities of the pituitary tumor microenvironment via single cell and spatial transcriptomic sequencing (Nr. Izp-2025/1-0304)

Version 1

Description

Pituitary neuroendocrine tumors (PitNETs) are the most common intracranial tumors, yet they rarely metastasize. Pituitary tissue exhibits plasticity, but the mechanisms that prevent cancer development are unclear. This study will use spatial transcriptomics and in vitro cell experiments to investigate SF1-line PitNETs, cell line models, and cancer cells. Objectives: 1) to identify spatial features that prevent malignancy by analyzing cell interactions, cell types, and pituitary plasticity; 2) to investigate the clinical applicability of markers from spatial transcriptomics data of gonadotropic PitNETs by comparing PitNETs with other tumors, searching for new therapeutic targets, and functionally investigating recent findings in the literature. 3) Perform integrated data analysis by linking spatial cell distribution to tumor cell composition and identifying clinical group, lineage and PitNET-specific localizations, biomarkers and common trends compared to other groups as well as reference data including PitNET, cancer and other neuroendocrine tumors, and take into account genetic background in this analysis. Functional experiments will use RNantisense A to investigate the role of genes recently identified in the literature and validate the novel findings of this project to advance the understanding of therapeutic targets for SF1 lineage PitNET. The project aims to uncover PitNET biology, improve treatments and provide information to other cancer research.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS LCS

Grant

Researchers

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Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Revealing the complexities of the pituitary tumor microenvironment via single cell and spatial transcriptomic sequencing \(Nr. lzp-2025/1-0304\)](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [LCS](#)

Data Management Plan | Revealing the complexities of the pituitary tumor microenvironment via single cell and spatial transcriptomic sequencing (Nr. lzp-2025/1-0304) LICENSE:AFL-3.0 DOI: - 01/04/2026

Project: [biomedicine](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The specific scientific objectives of the project are:

1) to identify spatial features preventing malignancy, analyzing cell interactions, cell types and pituitary plasticity by deconvoluting spatial transcriptomic data and extracting single cell-like information. We will use single nuclei sequencing data of PitNETs from previous studies to increase accuracy of deconvolution of cell types from spatial transcriptomics data to in the tumor surgery material (including immune cells and their functional state), ratio of cells expressing tumor lineage markers, compare SF1 lineage PitNET cell composition across tumors in search for common and distinct features that could be protective against malignant transformation.

2) Explore clinical applicability of markers from gonadotroph PitNET spatial transcriptomic data, comparing PitNETs to other tumors, seeking novel therapeutic targets and functional investigating recently proposed, such as DLK1, DDIT4, PMAIP1 and RCN1. This objective is aimed at performing functional experiments in cell lines using antisense RNAs to target expression of PitNET promoting genes (or their regulators) to assess their potential use for therapeutic targeting and tumor biology understanding. Which would help to answer question if PitNET microenvironment contains specific signatures of tumour suppressor gene and oncogene regulation. In addition, give insight to specific mechanisms that could be utilized for other malignant tumour type research and development of potential future therapies.

3) Perform integrated data analysis linking spatial cell distribution with tumor cell composition from single cell data and identifying clinical group, lineage and PitNET specific localizations, biomarkers and common trends when comparing to other groups as well as reference data including PitNET, cancerous tumor and other neuroendocrine tumors, and take genetic background into consideration when conducting this analysis. That could serve as a basis for further understanding of PitNET biology, and distinct features that could be used for improved treatment strategies for these tumours and potentially also indicate targets for further intervention research for other tumour types.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Clinical data
- Machine-readable text
- Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

- TIFF
- PNG
- XLS
- JSON
- Others

FASTQ, HDF5, MTX

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

TB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Single cell portal

Single Cell Portal

https://singlecell.broadinstitute.org/single_cell

id: https://singlecell.broadinstitute.org/single_cell?

type=study&page=1&terms=pituitary, Type: url

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

This data could help this project to identify cell types in pituitary, enhance annotation of the spatial maps and cell clusters. Allow to pinpoint rare cell types

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

GEO

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Gene Expression Omnibus

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

As long as repository is holding it.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Raitis Pečulis (0000-0003-1107-4550)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Ethics permission is acquired from relevant Medical Ethics Committee

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws
- Pseudonymization

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